

IMPROVING PRESERVATION AND ACCESS TO BORN-DIGITAL COLLECTIONS:

A CRITICAL DISABILITY AND INTERSECTIONALITY-INFORMED ASSESSMENT OF PRAXIS

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HELLO!

LOCATION

United States
Illinois (Chicago region)

Private research
university

ARCHIVES & SPECIAL COLLECTIONS

Non-circulating

Rare

Unique

Cultural Heritage
Institutional History

BORN-DIGITAL CONTENT

Special collections that
are natively electronic

Obsolete to current
formats/media
Web archives

QUESTIONS FOR YOU

Where are you from?

What do you hope to get out of this presentation?

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

As a cis het, able-bodied, white woman, I acknowledge my privileges and recognize the unique perspectives and lived experiences of those in the disabled and marginalized communities. I have attempted to approach this research with care and respect and recognize that I am not a representative voice of these communities.

DEFINITIONS

ACCESSIBILITY

Degrees by which products devices, services, environments, or facilities are usable to people physically, cognitively, and emotionally

ABLEISM

A bias rooted in the idea that those with full able-body physicality and sound mental health are superior to those with physical, cognitive, or mental impairments

BIGOTRY

Intolerance of differences; All the ways in which intentional, systemic, and unconscious beliefs cause oppressions based on various identities and circumstances

INTRODUCTION

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Great variabilities across historic and current born-digital collections create challenges for preservation and access

RESEARCH QUESTION

How does computing impact accessibility and marginalization of user communities for born-digital materials?

THESIS

Computer hardware and software design, algorithms, and metadata implicitly impact equitable preservation and access to the ever-increasing amounts of born-digital acquisitions.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

CRITICAL DISABILITY THEORY

Disability is a social construct and the disadvantages faced by those with physical, cognitive, and mental disabilities are the result of ableist perspectives and design

INTERSECTIONALITY THEORY

Examines how overlapping social identities and circumstances are related to and the byproduct of various disadvantages and discrimination

**“THE FIELD OF
CRITICAL DISABILITY
STUDIES HAS SELDOM
CONVERGED WITH LIS
RESEARCH.”
-EMMA MAY**

LITERATURE REVIEW

- Computer science
- Computing history
- Accessibility Legislation
- LIS Research
- LIS Accessibility Guidelines
- LIS Inclusivity Guidelines

LITERATURE REVIEW

- 3-part framework for identifying the biases in computing: Preexisting, Technical, and Emergent (Friedman & Nissenbaum, 1996)

PREEXISTING

Rooted in institutions,
practices, attitudes

Can be from society at
large or individual

TECHNICAL

Technological
constraints from tools,
algorithms,
pseudorandom number
generation

EMERGENT

User interactions

Actual user experience
does not match
intended design

LITERATURE REVIEW

- Computing bias study and accessibility legislation begins in the 1990s
 - (United Nations; Friedman & Nissenbaum, 1996)
- LIS research and guidelines focus on physical accessibility (2010-present)
- Growing consensus in Archival Science that access and use can be improved by highlighting authentic voices for the most marginalized communities (2020-present)

FINDINGS: ABLEISM

Computing hardware and software built for the users with full:

- visual & auditory functions
- limb symmetry
- full physical control
- reading ability & comprehension
- mid-level cognitive function

Assistive Technologies developed to address these differences

- Bulk is after 1990s Accessibility legislation
- Much iteration on AT hardware and software since
- Versions and operating systems create idiosyncrasies/challenges

FINDINGS: BIGOTRY

- Technologies present as objective, scientific, mathematical
- Unintentional dominance of white, cishet, American men developing computer hardware and software
- Biases are intangible and easily overlooked
- Software increasingly dependent on algorithms, machine learning, AI - risks of sustaining/growing bias in the code

IMPLICATIONS

FUTURE RESEARCH

- More CDT and Intersectionality Theory informed research on digital collections
- Emulation impacts
- Disability and marginalized user experience studies

THEORETICAL

- Digital Preservation
- Archival Administration
- Curatorial and Collection Development

POLICY

- Digital Preservation Actions
- Description and Arrangement
- Terms of Access and Use

PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS: BORN-DIGITAL COLLECTIONS

DIGITAL PRESERVATION

- Appraisal for storage
- Copies of content with accommodations
- Preservation metadata

ACCESSIONS AND PROCESSING

- Flexible workflows to allow modification for accommodation requests
- Document and publish limitations

ACCESS AND USE

- Easy and obvious to request accommodation
- Educating users
- Mindful of users' vulnerabilities
- Active listening

CONCLUSION

LIMITATIONS

Research conducted by someone outside the disability and marginalized communities

More comprehensive investigation on the potential for remediation or hindrance of AI

FINAL THOUGHTS

User-first approaches can reduce risks of causing harm from inherent biases rooted in ableism and bigotry

Prioritize the humanity of workers and users

THANK YOU

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